

Supporting Information

Free-standing electrochemically coated MoS_x based 3D-printed nanocarbon electrode for solid-state supercapacitor application

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Fig. S1. Dimensions of the 3D-printed electrodes (a) cylindrical shape with an arm, (b) interdigital-shape, and (c) CEITEC-shape.

Fig. S2. Photograph of electrodeposition set up for cylindrical-shaped electrode.

Fig. S3. Photographs of assembling of the two electrodes using PVA/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte in an open box : (a,b) interdigital-shaped and (c,d) CEITEC-shaped solid-state supercapacitor.

Fig. S4. Photographs of (a) cylindrical shaped electrode in three-electrode test system and (b,c) interdigital-shaped solid-state supercapacitor cell showing their free-standing nature.

area considered for electrochemical analysis (highlighted parts (blue))
 (a) = 54.95 mm², (b) = 92.24 mm², and (c) = 139.84 mm²

Fig. S5. (a), (b) and (c) shows the area considered for electrochemical analysis.

Fig. S6. Cyclic voltammetry study of MoS_x@GC at different potential window.

Fig. S7. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy spectra of MoS_x coated 3D-PE electrode (MoS_x@3D-PE), inset: a table showing atomic percentages of the constituent elements.

Fig S8. Cyclic voltammetry measurement for first 3 cycles at scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ for electrodeposition of MoS_x.

Fig. S9. Cyclic voltammetry study of the blank 3D-PE electrode.

Fig. S10. From Bode plot of EIS measurement: variation of (a) real and (b) imaginary specific capacitances with frequency of the interdigital-shaped solid-state supercapacitor cell.

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Fig. S11. (a) Photograph, (b) cyclic voltammetry, and (c) galvanostatic charge-discharge of CEITEC-shaped solid-state supercapacitor.

Table S1. Comparison of energy density and power density of the free-standing $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ with reported data

Materials	Electrolyte	Fabrication method	Energy density	Power density	Ref.
$\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$	PVA/ H_2SO_4	FDM printing/ electrodeposition	$0.20 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$	$16.26 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$	this work
$\text{MoS}_2/\text{PANI}/\text{CNT}$ composite paper	PVA/ H_2SO_4	filtration	0.013 Wh cm^{-3}	1.000 W cm^{-3}	1
MoS_2 wire type SC	PVA/LiOH	Ball milling	8.1 nW h cm^{-1}	0.145 uWcm^{-1}	2
MoS_2 nanosheet	PVA/ H_2SO_4	hydrothermal/ Inkjet printing	$0.215 \text{ mW h cm}^{-3}$	0.018 W cm^{-3}	3
1 T MoS_2 MSC	PVA/ H_2SO_4	femtosecond laser direct writing	15.6 mWh cm^{-3}	1.12 W cm^{-3}	4
Free-standing MXene- MoS_2 film	gelatin/borax/ ZnSO_4	direct laser etching	15.5 mWh cm^{-3} 7.2 mWh cm^{-3}	0.06 W cm^{-3} 0.97 W cm^{-3}	5
$\text{MoS}_2@r\text{GO}$	PVA/KOH	gravure printing	0.42 mWh cm^{-3}	13.1 mW cm^{-3}	6
1 T- MoS_2	PVA/ Na_2SO_4	hydrothermal	$43.1 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$	$500 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$	7
2H- MoS_2 nanoflowers	PVA/ Na_2SO_4	hydrothermal	16.4 Wh kg^{-1}	0.16 kW kg^{-1}	8
MoS_2 quantum sheet	PVA/ H_2SO_4	ball milling	14.46 Wh kg^{-1}	200 W kg^{-1}	9
MoS_2 -Ni foam	PVA- Na_2SO_4	solvothormal	5.4 Wh kg^{-1}	$\sim 590 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$	10
Vertical-slate-like $\text{MoS}_2@NI$ foam	$\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{PVA}$	hydrothermal	4.7 Wh kg^{-1}	650 W kg^{-1}	11

The areal specific capacitance [mF cm^{-2}] was calculated from the CV study using the Equation-S1:¹²

$$C_{sp} = \frac{\int_{V_1}^{V_2} I(V) dV}{v (V_2 - V_1) A} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where, $I(V)$ is the average current [mA] of the CV loop, v is the scan rate [mV s^{-1}], A is the total active area [cm^2], and V_1 and V_2 are the potential [V] limits in the CV study. For, the two-electrode test set up, the active area A includes the area of both electrodes.

Moreover, the areal specific capacitance [mF cm^{-2}] can also be calculated from the constant current discharging curve of galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) experiment using the Equation-S2: ¹²

$$C_{sp} = \frac{I \Delta t}{\Delta V A} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where, I is the constant current [mA], Δt is the total discharging time [s], ΔV is the discharge voltage [V] range and A is the total active area [cm^2].

The energy density [$\mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$] was calculated from C_{sp} [mF cm^{-2}] using the Equation-S3.¹³

$$E_{sp} = 0.5 \times C_{sp} \times \Delta V^2 \times \frac{1000}{3600} \quad (\text{S3})$$

The power density [$\mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$] was calculated using Equation-S4

$$P_{sp} = \frac{E_{sp}}{t} \times 3600 \quad (\text{S4})$$

where, t is the discharge time in s.

The real part and imaginary part of capacitances were calculated from Equations-S5 and S6, respectively.¹⁴

$$C'(\omega) = \frac{-Z''(\omega)}{\omega |Z(\omega)|^2} \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$C''(\omega) = \frac{Z'(\omega)}{\omega |Z(\omega)|^2} \quad (\text{S6})$$

where, $C'(\omega)$ is the real part of capacitance $C(\omega)$ and $C''(\omega)$ is the imaginary part of capacitance $C(\omega)$, and $Z'(\omega)$ and $Z''(\omega)$ are the real part and imaginary part of impedance $Z(\omega)$, respectively. ω is the angular frequency; where, $\omega = 2\pi f$, f is the frequency in Hz.

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